

Gaps and solutions to accelerate EU bioeconomy development

Bioeconomy financing analysis carried out by the ShapingBio project has revealed a series of 8 gaps currently limiting development of the bioeconomy in the EU.

These gaps have been identified in ShapingBio analysis with the stakeholder groups of investors and companies and will be verified with policy makers and other stakeholder groups

About

SHAPINGBIO

ShapingBio is an EU-funded project with the overall aim to support and accelerate bioeconomy innovation and the deployment of new knowledge in the EU and its member states.

ShapingBio aims to provide evidence-based and concrete information and recommendations for better policy alignment and stakeholder actions to realise the cross-sectoral potential of the bioeconomy and to reduce the fragmentation across biobased sectors and the food system, as well as in policies across regions, domains and governance levels.

www.shapingbio.eu

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Gap 1 Early-Stage Financing

Solutions

- Develop streamlined financial instruments for early-stage innovators.
- Offer pre-seed and seed funding combined with mentorship and business development.
- Strengthen university Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs) and teach entrepreneurial skills.

Gap 2 Scaling and Commercialisation

Solutions

- Adopt milestone-based funding disbursements to align with specific achievements.
- Provide scaling programs with targeted support for business development and market entry.
- Engage industrial experts in funding decisions to evaluate scaling potential effectively.

Gap 3 Capacity Building in Bioeconomy Companies

Solutions

- Create regional bioeconomy hubs with integrated financing and skills training.
- Enhance EU and national funding authorities' outreach and informational platforms.
- Establish proactive portfolio management by funding bodies for stronger company support.

Gap 4 Long-Term Innovation Project Funding

Solutions

- Introduce multi-stage funding programs to support projects throughout their lifecycle.
- Evaluate project progress with mechanisms for follow-on funding based on milestones.
- Coordinate funding pipelines across governance levels to avoid financing gaps.

Bioeconomy development gaps

And how to solve them

Gap 5 Access to Market

Solutions

- Implement stricter CO₂ taxes and direct subsidies for bio-based products.
- Align scaling funds with private sector needs through public equity schemes.
- Introduce scaling and entrepreneur support programmes to develop their investment readiness and strategic business connections.

Gap 6 Public-Private Collaboration

Solutions

- Establish structured public-private schemes to de-risk investments.
- Expand equity investment schemes to support high-risk projects and attract private capital.

Gap 7 Time Lag in EU Programme Implementation

Solutions

- Introduce adaptive work programmes for periodic reviews and adjustments.
- Implement fast-track procedures for urgent call revisions to address emerging global challenges.

Gap 8 Regulatory and Administrative Complexity

Solutions

- Simplify regulations and harmonise frameworks across governance levels.
- Standardise bioeconomy taxonomy and technology nomenclature.
- Introduce AI/machine learning tools to streamline proposal matching.